

A spectroscopic census of L Dwarfs observed by Gaia

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Abstract

The ESA cornerstone mission Gaia will revolutionise astronomy observing objects as diverse as minor planets, stars, and galaxies out to QSOs. We estimate that Gaia will observe directly ~ 500 L0 to L4 dwarfs and a handful of L5 to T1 dwarfs, providing precision of 0.1–0.3 mas in parallax for these objects, and tangential velocities at the level of 10–30 m s⁻¹. As these objects are very close, the perspective acceleration will change both the parallax and the proper motion over the time frame of the mission, leading to “astrometric” radial velocities with errors of 50 km s⁻¹. However, to fully exploit the extremely accurate and precise astrometric data, it is fundamental to obtain better radial velocities. In this contribution we present the preliminary results from a large campaign conducted with OSIRIS on the GTC and X-shooter on the VLT to measure radial velocities for L dwarfs that will be observed by Gaia. The spectra will be used to determine radial velocities, spectral indices, identify possible unresolved binaries, and further investigate the peculiar objects in the sample. Combined with the Gaia results this will be a incomparable dataset for many studies.

1 Introduction

L dwarfs are a mix of objects that have masses encompassing the smallest stars, brown dwarfs and the largest planets. The first L dwarf was discovered in 1988 orbiting the white dwarf GD 165 (Becklin & Zuckerman, 1988). This object remained unique for a decade before an avalanche of objects were found in the infrared sky surveys and later the deep optical surveys. These new objects led to the definition of the new L spectral class (Kirkpatrick et al., 1999) with temperatures ranging from 2500 K to 1500 K.

L dwarfs are very different to the majority of higher mass stars in that they do not spend most of their lifetime with slowly varying physical parameters on a “main sequence”, instead changing significantly with age. Models predict a L4/L5 type object could be as diverse as a 7 Myr old 9 Jupiter mass planet, a 90 Myr old 30 Jupiter mass brown dwarf or a an 8 Gyr old 80 Jupiter mass low-mass star (see e.g. Burrows et al., 2001). The degeneracy between age and mass in this spectral range is not present for higher mass stars. This degeneracy makes L dwarfs very difficult to understand but once we have correctly calibrated age, or equivalently mass indicators, it will prove to be one of their greatest strengths – L dwarfs will become exquisite celestial clocks.

These objects provide test cases for the physics of large planet atmospheres, they allow us to examine the forma-

tion mechanisms of low-mass stars, the combination of a long lifetime, evolution with age and ubiquity will render them very powerful chronometers to understand the Galaxy and its substructures. As with other celestial objects their distance is a crucial observational parameter that Gaia will find for a limited sample (Smart, 2014).

Since the Gaia L dwarfs will be close, and in general will have a large proper motion and non-zero radial velocities, the astrometric parameters calculated by Gaia will be subject to our ability to measure the perspective acceleration and secular change in the parallax. This has been studied in detail for the Hipparcos stars in Dravins et al. (1999). The “astrometric” radial velocities from the secular change in parallax are given by

$$v_r = -A \frac{\dot{\pi}}{\pi^2}, \quad (1)$$

where A is the AU, which we express as 9.77792×10^8 mas km yr s⁻¹ (note the non standard units), π is the parallax in mas, which ranges from 300 to 10 mas and has a median of 50 for the Gaia L dwarf, and $\dot{\pi}$ is the secular change in parallax in mas yr⁻¹. The associated error is given by

$$\epsilon(v_r) \simeq \sqrt{12} A \frac{\epsilon(\pi)}{L\pi^2}, \quad (2)$$

where L is the mission length in years, which we assume

to be 5 for Gaia, and $\epsilon(\pi)$ the parallax error, which ranges from 0.05 to 0.2 mas for the magnitude range occupied by Gaia L dwarfs. For all but the closest Gaia L dwarfs this error will always be above 50 km s^{-1} . This can be seen as a requirement, i.e. an unknown radial velocity will only introduce significant errors in the parallax for the closest objects.

The ‘‘astrometric’’ radial velocities from the perspective acceleration (i.e. the change in proper motion) are given by

$$v_r = -A \frac{\dot{\mu}}{2\pi\mu}, \quad (3)$$

where μ is the total proper motion in mas yr^{-1} , and $\dot{\mu}$ is the perspective acceleration in mas yr^{-2} . The error in ‘‘astrometric’’ radial velocities from the perspective acceleration is given by

$$\epsilon(v_r) \simeq \sqrt{15} A \frac{\epsilon(\mu)}{L\pi\mu}, \quad (4)$$

where $\epsilon(\mu)$ is the proper motion error (in mas yr^{-1}). The Gaia L dwarf sample have proper motions from 2000 mas yr^{-1} to 100 mas yr^{-1} and a median of 300 mas yr^{-1} . Assuming median values of $\pi = 50 \text{ mas}$, $\mu = 300 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$, and an $\epsilon(\mu)$ of 0.1 mas yr^{-1} we find the error in ‘‘astrometric’’ radial velocities is around 50 km s^{-1} . This means external estimates of the radial velocities can be used in the reduction routine to constrain the solution or can be used as a independent check on the astrometric solution. Since the ground based spectroscopic radial velocities are an order of magnitude better than the ‘‘astrometric’’ ones this is a rare case where we have more precise independent parameters with which to check the Gaia results.

2 Science goals

The goal of this project is to complete the medium-resolution spectroscopic census of all known L dwarfs that are within the Gaia magnitude limit ($G \sim 20.7 \text{ mag}$). In the left panel of Figure 1 we plot the distribution in equatorial coordinates of the L and T dwarfs that we consider candidates for Gaia observation. We estimate this distribution is missing 25% of the objects due to incompleteness in the Galactic plane (Smart, 2014).

In the right panel we show the 2MASS J magnitude distribution. The majority of the potential targets are between J of 14 and 16, making them ideal targets for high signal-to-noise ratio spectroscopy. Previous studies based on X-shooter spectra (e.g. Marocco et al., 2014, 2015) have shown that we can achieve a precision of $1\text{--}5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ on the measured radial velocity of L dwarfs even with signal-to-noise-ratio as low as 10.

A number of observing campaigns have been dedicated to measuring radial velocity for L and T dwarfs. In particular, we refer here to Schmidt et al. (2010) who determined the radial velocity for a sample of 484 L dwarfs from the SDSS, and Blake et al. (2010) who derived the radial velocity for a sample of 59 late-M and L dwarfs using NIRSPEC on Keck.

A total of 322 early-to-mid L dwarfs in the current list of objects visible to Gaia have measured radial velocities,

a sample of which are listed in Table 1. The radial velocity distribution, and the distribution on the uncertainties are plotted in Figure 2, in the left and right panel respectively. The radial velocity distribution appears clearly Gaussian, centered at -2.3 km s^{-1} and with a dispersion of 34.1 km s^{-1} . The shift of the center of the distribution from zero is probably due to the Solar motion, while the dispersion is consistent with the dispersion measured for stellar objects. When looking at the uncertainties distribution, there appear to be a clear break below 4 km s^{-1} . Out of the 322 Gaia L dwarfs with measured radial velocities, 184 are measured to a precision of better than 10 km s^{-1} , but only 40 of them are measured down to a precision of 1 km s^{-1} or better. The vast majority of these objects (276) are in the northern hemisphere, where the (Schmidt et al., 2010) and (Blake et al., 2010) programs were focused. there is therefore a desperate need for radial velocity follow-up of the southern population of L dwarfs, even more so considering that the majority of the nearby young associations are predominantly located in the southern sky.

3 Preliminary results & future work

The program was awarded 65 hours on GTC/OSIRIS and obtained medium resolution optical spectra for 55 Gaia L dwarfs. Some of the spectra obtained can be seen in Figure 3, sorted in descending order of spectral type. The spectra will be used to determine radial velocities (with an expected precision of $\sim 5\text{--}10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), spectral indices, identify possible unresolved binaries, and further investigate the peculiar objects in the sample. The program was awarded other 49.1 hours on VLT/Xshooter, to complete the southern hemisphere part of the campaign (93 targets, observations ongoing). All the spectra will be made publicly available via the M-, L- and T-dwarf Archive of Interest for Astrophysics (MAIA, <http://exoterrae.eu/maia/>).

We will iterate between models and full simulations with the spectra composition, age and mass indicators and the Gaia derived galactic and stellar population parameters to construct a coherent, consistent picture of the L dwarfs in the local solar neighborhood.

In particular we will achieve a more precise, accurate and robust calibration of the spectroscopic age/metallicity/surface gravity indicators by identifying a large sample of benchmark objects, i.e. L and T dwarfs with well constrained atmospheric parameters. In this respect, the kinematics are key to identify binary systems (where the atmospheric parameters of the L dwarf can be inferred from its stellar companion), members of clusters and young moving groups (where the cluster age and metallicity can be applied to the L dwarf), and to constrain the age via population studies.

Gaia will greatly improve our ability to identify these kind of systems by providing parallaxes and proper motions for a huge sample of L dwarfs. These will have parallaxes with a precision of 0.1 to 0.3 mas , providing distances with relative errors of $1\text{--}10\%$ and tangential velocities at the level of $10\text{--}30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. However these objects are too faint for the the Gaia Radial Velocity Spectrometer, hence the need for ground based medium- to high-resolution spectroscopic observations for the deter-

Figure 1: Left: the position on the sky (in equatorial coordinates) of the L and T dwarfs (red and blue circles, respectively) that will be observed by Gaia. Right: the 2MASS J magnitude distribution for the same sample. These are all relatively bright objects, therefore suitable for high signal-to-noise ratio, medium resolution spectroscopy.

Table 1: A sample of the list of L dwarfs visible by Gaia with measured radial velocities. The complete list is available online at <http://exoterrae.eu/maia/>. References: 1- Kirkpatrick et al. (2010); 2- Blake et al. (2010); 3- Schmidt et al. (2010); 4- West et al. (2008).

Discovery Name	R.A. (hh:mm:ss.ss)	Dec. (dd:mm:ss.s)	Gaia G (mag)	Radial velocity (km s ⁻¹)	Ref	Spectral type
2MASS J00040288-6410358	00:04:02.88	-64:10:35.8	20.387	-57.0 ± 50.0	1	L1 γ
GJ 1001 B	00:04:34.84	-40:44:05.8	18.708	32.9 ± 0.2	2	L5
2MASSW J0015447+351603	00:15:44.76	+35:16:02.6	18.695	-37.3 ± 0.2	2	L2
2MASS J00163762-1039106	00:16:37.62	-10:39:10.6	19.755	-1.6 ± 24.8	3;4	L0
SDSS J001911.65+003017.6	00:19:11.65	+00:30:17.6	19.506	-4.5 ± 15.3	3	L1
2MASS J00220932-0110399	00:22:09.32	-01:10:49.9	20.134	-30.3 ± 41.0	3;4	L0
SDSS J002611.45-094341.1	00:26:11.47	-09:43:40.6	20.177	-20.7 ± 3.1	3	L1
LSPM J0036+1821	00:36:16.17	+18:21:10.4	17.554	19.0 ± 0.2	2	L3.5
SDSS J003843.99+134339.5	00:38:43.98	+13:43:39.5	20.479	28.0 ± 12.7	3	L1
2MASS J00452143+1634446	00:45:21.43	+16:34:44.6	17.878	3.4 ± 0.2	2	L2 β

Figure 2: The radial velocity (left panel) and uncertainties (right panel) distribution for the L dwarf that are visible to Gaia. Radial velocities follow a Gaussian distribution, centered at -2.3 km s^{-1} and with a dispersion of 34.1 km s^{-1} , while their uncertainties distribution shows a clear break below 4 km s^{-1}

mination of radial velocities, spectral indices, and metallicity and age indicators necessary to fully exploit these benchmarks.

For instance, the confirmation of moving group members requires radial velocity uncertainties of less than $1 - 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as they overlap in kinematical parameter space. Moving groups in fact have typical UVW velocities dispersion of $\approx 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (e.g. Malo et al., 2013), and we require radial velocities for Gaia L dwarfs to robustly constrain their membership. Similar considerations apply to benchmark systems (see e.g. Pinfield et al., 2006).

Combined with the Gaia results, the radial velocities obtained by this project will be an incomparable dataset for many studies, allowing us to identify dozen of benchmark systems.

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Figure 3: A sample of the objects observed so far, sorted in descending order of spectral type.